

Digital Marketing Skill Needs of Business Education Students in the Promotion of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14873072>

Abstract

The study examined the digital marketing skill needs of business education students in the promotion of small and medical scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research was adopted for the study. The population for the study comprised 420 respondents which comprised 25 business educators and 395 business education students. The sample size was 210 respondents which was determined using stratified proportionate random sampling technique. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection titled “Digital Marketing Skill Needs of Students Questionnaire (DMSNSQ)”. The instrument was validated by three specialists. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded 0.81 and 0.79 for cluster 1 and 2 respectively with an overall reliability index of 0.80 which showed that the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic. The findings of the study revealed that social media and Search engine optimization skills are needed by business education students in the promotion of small and medical scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. It is recommended that the curriculum for business education students should include specialized courses in social media marketing and search engine optimization (SEO) to enhance their digital marketing skills. Additionally, workshops and practical training sessions should be organized to provide hands-on experience in applying these skills to promote small and medium-scale enterprises effectively.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Skills, Business Education, SME Promotion, Students

Introduction

Small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) are recognized for their ability to handle diverse projects based on factors such as financial resources, capital investment, employee count, sales capacity, annual turnover, and overall financial strength (Osim, 2010). In Nigeria, SMEs are defined as independent businesses that do not act as subsidiaries and employ fewer than a specified number of workers. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are vital contributors to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with their impact felt through multiple avenues such as employment generation, economic diversification, and poverty alleviation (Ezeani, 2011). Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) are crucial for economic growth as they create jobs and foster innovation, particularly in developing regions. They contribute significantly to poverty reduction by enhancing income generation and improving living standards. Additionally, SMEs help diversify the economy by promoting local entrepreneurship and reducing dependence on large corporations.

In Nigeria, SMEs constitute about 96% of businesses and contribute 48% to the national GDP, underscoring their importance to the economy. Their flexibility allows them to operate in diverse sectors, providing essential goods and services while creating job opportunities, as seen in Enugu State where they help reduce unemployment (Effiong & Akpan, 2016). SMEs' adaptability fosters innovation and competitiveness, ensuring their resilience even in challenging economic conditions (Okoro & Agbo, 2019). Supporting the growth of SMEs through favorable policies can further enhance their role in Nigeria's economic development. Additionally, marketing educators must equip business students with digital marketing skills to integrate them effectively into the SME sector. These skills are crucial for future marketers to adapt to professional demands, particularly in the digital age.

Business education aims to equip students with the skills necessary for career success, consumer roles, and entrepreneurship, aligning with the goals of SMEs in driving economic growth (Aliyu, 2013). By mastering digital marketing, students can enhance the visibility, customer engagement, and sales of SMEs, contributing to job creation and economic stability (Effiong & Akpan, 2016). This fosters innovation and entrepreneurship, benefiting not only individual businesses but the overall economy (Obi, 2017). Marketing is essential for informing consumers about products and building relationships, and business education teaches students to develop these skills (Reijonen, 2010). Digital marketing involves mastering the four Ps—product, price, place, and promotion—through cognitive, technical, and interpersonal abilities (Gidado & Akaeze, 2014). Online platforms like Google and social media tools provide businesses with opportunities to optimize visibility and engage customers directly (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Google Ads, Analytics, and SEO help businesses target specific audiences and measure campaign success (Ryan, 2017). Social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram enable real-time, personalized interactions, enhancing customer loyalty (Tuten & Solomon, 2018). These tools allow businesses to build brand awareness and increase their reach (OECD, 2016). The synergy between search engines and social media forms the foundation of effective digital marketing strategies (Ryan, 2017).

Social media skills encompass the ability to effectively use social media platforms to communicate, engage, and market products or services. These skills include creating and managing content, analyzing engagement metrics, and utilizing various tools to optimize social media strategies (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). Social media plays a vital role in connecting people globally, fostering communication and community building across diverse locations and cultures (Okechukwu & Ukeh, 2022). It serves as a powerful tool for businesses and organizations to reach wider audiences, promote their products, and engage with customers in real-time. Additionally, social media platforms provide a space for information dissemination, enabling users to stay informed about current events, trends, and educational content. Proficiency in social media skills also involves understanding platform algorithms and trends to enhance online presence and audience interaction (Tuten & Solomon, 2017). Mastery of these skills is essential for building brand reputation and driving business success in the digital age (Kietzmann et al., 2011). Both social media skills and search engine optimization (SEO) skills are essential for enhancing online visibility and driving traffic, as they collectively contribute to a comprehensive digital marketing strategy.

Search engine optimization (SEO) skills are essential for business education students, as they encompass the understanding of web design, programming, and the creation of content that ranks well on search engines such as Google and Yahoo (Marcolin, Miroudot, & Squicciarini, 2016).

Mastery of SEO enables students to design not only visually appealing but also highly functional web content, which is critical for the digital presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This expertise ensures that the content created is optimized for search engines, thereby improving the visibility and reach of businesses in an increasingly competitive online marketplace (Nguyen, 2020). This is particularly important for SMEs that rely on effective online advertising to attract and retain customers in the digital age (Obi & Chukwu, 2018). In Nigeria, where internet penetration is rapidly growing, these skills are invaluable in helping SMEs leverage online platforms to expand their market reach and boost sales (Akinyemi, 2019). Thus, incorporating SEO into business education curricula is crucial for equipping students with the tools they need to contribute to the success of local enterprises.

Business education students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, require robust digital marketing skills to effectively promote small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs). Proficiency in social media is crucial, as it enables students to create targeted marketing campaigns, engage with potential customers, and build brand awareness for SMEs. Similarly, skills in search engine optimization (SEO) are essential for improving the online visibility of SMEs, driving organic traffic, and enhancing their search engine rankings. By mastering these digital tools, students can help SMEs increase their online presence and reach a broader audience. The integration of these skills into business education curricula will better prepare students for the evolving digital marketplace.

Research indicates that digital marketing skills are crucial for Business Education students aiming to promote small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A study by Mbah et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of social media skills, noting that platforms like Facebook and Instagram are vital for reaching local audiences and driving engagement for SMEs (Mbah et al., 2022). Additionally, the ability to utilize search engine optimization (SEO) techniques is emphasized by Adeoye & Akinlabi (2023), who argued that effective SEO strategies can enhance the online visibility of SMEs, leading to increased traffic and potential sales (Adeoye & Akinlabi, 2023).

The integration of these skills into business education curricula is seen as essential for equipping students with practical knowledge that can directly impact the growth of SMEs. Research by Alabi et al. (2024) supported this, suggesting that hands-on training in digital marketing, including SEO and social media management, significantly boosts students' competence and confidence (Alabi, Chukwu & Nwosu, 2024). Furthermore, a recent study by Eze et al. (2024) identifies a gap in current educational programmes, recommending a curriculum overhaul to include comprehensive digital marketing training (Eze, Ibe & Nnamdi, 2024).

The success of SMEs increasingly depends on leveraging digital marketing strategies like social media and SEO, which are critical for business growth and customer engagement (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter provide cost-effective channels for real-time interactions, personalized marketing, and enhanced customer satisfaction (Tuten & Solomon, 2018). Proficiency in social media marketing enables business education students to craft engaging content and analyze metrics, boosting SME visibility (Ryan, 2017). SEO, which improves website rankings and organic traffic, is another essential skill for students aiming to help SMEs thrive (Ledford, 2020). By mastering SEO, students can assist SMEs in reaching more customers and improving their online presence (Fishkin & Høgenhaven, 2013). Educators must integrate hands-on training in social media and SEO into the business education curriculum to prepare students for the evolving digital landscape (Kingsnorth, 2019). Ongoing professional development in emerging digital marketing strategies is also crucial due to rapid

technological advancements (Strauss & Frost, 2016). In Nigeria, social media and SEO are essential tools for SMEs to engage with broader audiences and drive business growth (Nkamnebe, 2017). Training in these areas is vital for business education students to support SMEs' success in competitive markets like Bayelsa State (Ajayi & Mbah, 2021). Ultimately, these skills not only benefit individual SMEs but also contribute to regional economic development (Eze et al., 2020). Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the digital marketing skill needs of business education students and their potential impact on promoting SMEs within tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid expansion of digital technologies has transformed business practices, particularly in the marketing domain. Despite this, business education students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, often lack the necessary digital marketing skills to effectively support and promote small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs). This gap in skills poses a significant challenge, as SMEs rely increasingly on digital marketing skills to reach and engage their target audiences. Furthermore, there is a noticeable deficiency in the integration of social media and search engine optimization (SEO) skills in the curriculum for business education students. Consequently, these students are inadequately prepared to leverage digital platforms for promoting SMEs. This inadequacy affects the ability of SMEs to compete effectively in the market and hinders their growth potential. The problem is compounded by the rapid evolution of digital marketing tools and practices, which requires ongoing updates to educational content and training methods. The lack of hands-on experience and practical application of these skills further exacerbates the issue. Therefore, there is a critical need to identify and address the specific digital marketing skill requirements of business education students, particularly in relation to social media and SEO. This study explored these needs to enhance the effectiveness of digital marketing education and support the promotion of SMEs in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the social media skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?
2. What are the search engine optimization (SEO) skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of business educators and business education students on the social media skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of business educators and business education students on the search engine optimization (SEO) skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Methods

Descriptive survey research was adopted for the study. According to Kothari and Garg (2014), descriptive survey research design is a type of research methodology that aims to describe the characteristics, behaviours, attitudes, or opinions of a population or phenomenon under investigation. The population for the study comprised 420 respondents which comprised 25 business educators and 395 business education students. The sample size was 84 respondents which was 10 percent of the population and it was determined using stratified proportionate random sampling technique. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection titled “Digital Marketing Skill Needs of Students Questionnaire (DMSNSQ)”. The instrument was validated by three specialists. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded 0.81 and 0.79 for cluster 1 and 2 respectively with an overall reliability index of 0.80 which showed that the instrument was reliable. The researcher used mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. In rating the mean, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: Strongly Agree (SA) = 3.50-4.00; Agree (A) = 2.50-3.49; Disagree (D) = 1.50-2.49; Strongly Disagree (SD) = 0.00-1.49. The interpretation of the test of hypotheses was based on the significance (sig.) values from the SPSS output. The null hypotheses were not rejected when the probability values are greater than 0.05, but rejected when the probability values are less than 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the social media skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviations of business educators and business education students on the social media skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

ITEMS		Business Educators 5		Students 79		Overall 84		n = 84
S/N	The following social media skills are needed by business education students for promoting SMEs:	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
1	Introducing company products to customers for direct access services through Whatsapp.	2.52	.84	2.56	.85	2.54	.85	A
2	Creating value added activities for product branding through twitter.	2.58	.87	2.62	.86	2.60	.87	A
3	Creating sale services relationship and opportunities for influence interaction with customers through feedback.	2.61	.88	2.54	.88	2.58	.88	A
4	Expanding sales output through mutual relationship using Instagram.	2.58	.97	2.54	.94	2.56	.96	A
5	Regulating purchase behaviour of customer to increase productivity target through Instagram.	2.51	.84	2.55	.81	2.53	.83	A
Cluster Mean/SD		2.56	.88	2.57	.87	2.56	.88	A

The table presents the mean scores and standard deviations of business educators and business education students on the social media skills needed to promote small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Bayelsa State. All five skills listed were rated as necessary (denoted by "A") by both groups, with overall weighted mean scores ranging from 2.53 to 2.60. The cluster mean for all items was 2.56 with a standard deviation of 0.88, indicating a consistent agreement among respondents on the importance of these social media skills. These skills include introducing company products through WhatsApp, creating value-added activities on Twitter, and expanding sales via Instagram.

Research Question 2: What are the search engine optimization (SEO) skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviations of business educators and business education students on the search engine skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	Business Educators 5		Students 79		Overall 84		Dec
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
6	Creating animation concept to demonstrate the service of the company to attract consumers.	2.58	.89	2.63	.86	2.61	.88	A
7	Activating a web-browser as default in order to particularize optimize easy search.	2.54	.85	2.56	.89	2.55	.87	A
8	Customizing the browser for easy machine booting and navigation of optimization themes.	2.57	.84	2.55	.83	2.56	.84	A
9	Creating page authority for domains consents.	2.50	.91	2.54	.90	2.53	.91	A
10	Creating keyword research result pages for optimization domain display.	2.55	.88	2.62	.84	2.59	.86	A
Cluster Mean/SD		2.55	.87	2.58	.86	2.57	.87	A

The table presents the mean scores and standard deviations for various search engine optimization (SEO) skills needed by business education students, as rated by business educators and students, along with the overall scores. The cluster mean for business educators is 2.55 (SD = 0.87), for students is 2.58 (SD = 0.86), and for both groups combined is 2.57 (SD = 0.87), indicating a general agreement on the need for these SEO skills, all rated as "Agree" (A). The skills include creating animation concepts, customizing browsers, and managing page authority, with scores showing that there is a consistent perception of the importance of these skills for promoting SMEs. The weighted mean reflects a moderate consensus on the SEO skills required, with business education students and educators both valuing these competencies for effective online promotion of small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Hypotheses

1. **There is no significant difference between the mean scores of business educators and business education students on the social media skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.**

Table 3: Summary of t-test of business educators and business education students on the social media skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	P-value	Decision
Business Educators	5	2.56	.88	82	.090	Ho ₁ not rejected
Students	79	2.57	.87			

The table presents a t-test analysis comparing the mean scores of business educators and business education students regarding social media skill needs for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. With a p-value of .090, which is greater than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho₁) is not rejected. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the two groups. Both business educators and students have similar views on the social media skill needs for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises.

2. **There is no significant difference between the mean scores of business educators and business education students on the search engine optimization (SEO) skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.**

Table 4: Summary of t-test of business educators and business education students on the search engine optimization (SEO) skill needs of business education students for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	P-value	Decision
Business Educators	5	2.55	.87	82	.086	Ho ₂ not rejected
Students	79	2.58	.86			

The table provides a t-test analysis comparing the mean scores of business educators and business education students on the SEO skill needs for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The mean scores for both business educators (2.55) and students (2.58) are very close, with standard deviations of 0.87 and 0.86, respectively. With a p-value of .086, which is higher than the common significance threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) is not rejected. This suggests that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of business educators and students regarding the importance of SEO skills. Both groups share similar views on the SEO skill needs for promoting small and medium-scale enterprises.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings highlighted the importance of social media skills for business education students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. These skills are crucial for effectively promoting and managing small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Bayelsa State. Mastery of social media can enhance

marketing efforts, customer engagement, and overall business growth for these enterprises. This aligns with the views of Afolabi and Oladipo (2020), who emphasized that social media proficiency significantly contributes to the success of SMEs by enabling effective communication and marketing strategies. Similarly, Oji et al. (2017) argued that social media platforms are essential tools for business education students to develop competencies that support the sustainability and growth of small businesses.

The study's findings revealed that search engine optimization (SEO) skills are essential for business education students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. These skills are necessary for effectively promoting small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) by increasing their online visibility and attracting potential customers. With a strong grasp of SEO, students can help these businesses rank higher in search engine results, leading to increased traffic, better customer engagement, and ultimately, business growth. This view is supported by Ojo and Adebayo (2021), who argued that SEO plays a crucial role in enhancing the online presence of SMEs, thereby boosting their competitive advantage. Similarly, Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) highlighted the importance of SEO in digital marketing, noting that it is a key factor in driving organic traffic and improving business outcomes.

Conclusion

The study's findings highlight the critical importance of social media and search engine optimization (SEO) skills for business education students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, particularly in promoting small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs). These digital skills have been identified as essential tools for enhancing the visibility and competitiveness of SMEs in today's technology-driven market. The integration of these skills into the business education curriculum is therefore imperative to equip students with the necessary expertise to support and grow SMEs. By doing so, business education can play an important role in fostering economic development and entrepreneurship in Bayelsa State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were proffered:

1. The curriculum for business education students should include specialized courses in social media marketing and search engine optimization (SEO) to enhance their digital marketing skills.
2. Workshops and practical training sessions should be organized to provide hands-on experience in applying these skills to promote small and medium-scale enterprises effectively.

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